

1 A Supplementary Material

2 A.1 Class-unbalanced setting.

3 In realistic scenarios, the class distributions of the query sets could be arbitrary and not necessarily
 4 uniform, which could harm the performance of transductive inference Veilleux et al. (2021). To further
 5 verify the effectiveness of our method, we conduct tests in the same unbalanced setting as Veilleux
 6 et al. (2021). Specifically, the query set is randomly distributed using a Dirichlet distribution with
 7 parameter $\alpha = 2$ instead of a uniform distribution. Table 1 shows the 5-way 1-shot and 5-way 5-shot
 8 results on *miniImageNet* and *tieredImageNet*. It can be observed that the methods all undergo a
 9 dramatic performance drop due to the class-unbalanced setting, and our method outperforms other
 models by about 2% and 3% margins in 5-way 1-shot and 5-way 5-shot tasks, respectively.

	mini-ImageNet		tiered-ImageNet	
Method	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot
Entropy-min	60.4	76.2	62.9	77.3
protoLP [†]	62.7	67.1	66.2	68.5
PT-MAP [†]	64.4	69.4	68.4	73.6
LaplacianShot	68.1	83.2	73.5	86.8
TIM	69.8	81.6	75.8	85.4
BD-CSPN	70.4	82.3	75.4	85.9
α -TIM	69.8	84.8	76.0	87.8
DIPO (ours)	72.1	87.8	78.0	91.1

Table 1: The classification accuracy (%) on *miniImageNet* and *tieredImageNet* in the class-unbalanced setting (with backbone WRN-28-10 in 5-way, 1-shot and 5-shot protocols over 10,000 few-shot tasks). "†" indicates that we have re-implemented the method in the same class-unbalanced setting. Other results are retrieved from Veilleux et al. (2021). The best results are highlighted in bold.

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11 A.2 Hyperparameter Tuning

12 The hyperparameters are tuned on the validation sets using WRN28-10 (unless the cross-domain
 13 scenario Chen et al. (2019) uses ResNet-18), and we choose the values that result in the best
 14 performance. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the hyperparameter settings.

Dataset	Setting	Hyperparameters
<i>miniImageNet</i>	5-way 1-shot	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (5, 14, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (5, 11, 1)$
	5-way 1-shot, Unbalance	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (2, 6, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot, Unbalance	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (1, 1, 1)$
<i>tieredImageNet</i>	5-way 1-shot	$k = 351, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (5, 12, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot	$k = 351, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (8, 8, 1)$
	5-way 1-shot, Unbalance	$k = 351, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (2, 6, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot, Unbalance	$k = 351, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (1, 1, 1)$
CUB	5-way 1-shot	$k = 58, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (5, 11, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot	$k = 58, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (6, 11, 1)$
CIFAR-FS	5-way 1-shot	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (7, 12, 1)$
	5-way 5-shot	$k = 64, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (6, 9, 1)$
cross-domain (<i>miniImageNet</i> \rightarrow CUB)	5-way 5-shot	$k = 8, \beta = 0.5, tuple = (4, 12, 1)$

Table 2: The hyperparameter setting of DIPO. "Unbalance" means the class-unbalanced setting Veilleux et al. (2021).

Figure 1: Left: Accuracy of the model tested on the validation set (blue) and testing set (red) when increasing the number of relevant base classes k on *miniImageNet* and CIFAR-FS. Right: Accuracy of the model tested on the validation set (blue) and testing set (red) when increasing the number of relevant base classes k on CUB and cross-domain scenario (*miniImageNet* \rightarrow CUB).

15 **The choice of k .** The choice of the number k of relevant base classes plays an essential role in
 16 approximating the intra-class diversity of the few-shot class. Figure 1 shows the 5-way 5-shot
 17 accuracy on different datasets when tuning the hyperparameter k . Depending on the difference in the
 18 domain shift, the optimal value of k varies. It is evident that datasets with a smaller domain shift (like
 19 *tieredImageNet*, CIFAR-FS, and CUB) require a larger k , whereas datasets with a greater domain
 20 shift (like the cross-domain scenario *miniImageNet* \rightarrow CUB) need a smaller k . By transferring the
 21 intra-class diversity from the k relevant base classes, we effectively solve the issue of non-estimable
 22 intra-class diversity inherent in the few-shot class.

23 **The choice of β .** Figure 2(left) shows the 5-way 1-shot accuracy on *miniImageNet* when tuning the
 24 power β for Tukey’s transformation. Note that Tukey’s transformation maintains the original feature
 25 representations when $\beta = 1$. It can be observed that the curves of the validation set (blue) and testing
 26 set (red) converge at the same β ($\beta = 0.5$) that achieves the best performance. With an appropriate
 27 value of β , the transformation can render the feature distribution more Gaussian-like, effectively
 28 embedding the intra-class diversity in the covariance matrix.

29 **The choice of tuple $(m, N_{iter}, step)$.** The tuple $(m, N_{iter}, step)$ is used to illustrate the number
 30 of query neighbors at each iteration and the number of iterations, where m is the number of query
 31 neighbors for the first iteration, N_{iter} is the number of iterations, and $step$ is the incremental increase
 32 in m for each subsequent iteration. For simplicity, we set $step = 1$ and investigate the effect of m
 33 and N_{iter} . Figure 2(right) is the contour plot that illustrates how the 5-way 1-shot accuracy changes
 34 with m and N_{iter} on the validation set of *miniImageNet*, where m and N_{iter} are integers from 1 to
 35 15. It can be observed that as m and N_{iter} increase, the accuracy tends to be higher, indicating that
 36 more suitable query samples are utilized. However, the accuracy does not increase steadily. The
 37 explanation may be that too many unlabeled query samples introduce bias in the direction of sample
 38 density growth.

39 A.3 The correlation between sample quality and density.

40 To illustrate the correlation between sample quality and density, we design a toy simulation of a binary
 41 classification task. Many studies Hu et al. (2021); Yang et al. (2021); Zhu & Koniusz (2022); Xu et al.
 42 (2022); Zhu & Koniusz (2023) explicitly or implicitly assume that features of the same class conform
 43 to a specific distribution (usually a Gaussian distribution). Thus, we let $\mathcal{C}_1 = \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, \Sigma_1)$, $\mathcal{C}_2 =$
 44 $\mathcal{N}(\mu_2, \Sigma_2)$ be two Gaussian distributions, where $\mu_1 = [-a, 0]$, $\mu_2 = [a, 0]$, $\Sigma_1 = \Sigma_2 = I$. The
 45 sample density of points sampled from a distribution is positively correlated with the probability
 46 density function Comaniciu & Meer (2002). For a better illustration, we scale the probability
 47 density function by a scale factor of β to estimate the sample density of a point. We learn decision
 48 boundaries using the Nearest-Centroid Classifier Snell et al. (2017), which first averages the points of each class
 49 in the support set to form class prototypes and then assigns the query points to the class of the nearest

Figure 2: Left: Accuracy of the model tested on the validation set (blue) and testing set (red) when increasing the power β in Tukey's transformation. Right: Contour plot visualization of 5-way 1-shot accuracy over m and N_{iter} on the validation set of *miniImageNet*. Each point represents a test with associated parameters.

Figure 3: Classification accuracy vs the average sample density from two class prototypes.

50 prototypes. We randomly sample 10,000 1-shot tasks with $a = 1$ and $\beta = 25$ for the simulation
 51 experiment.

52 As shown in Figure 3, there is a connection between classification accuracy and the average sample
 53 density from two class prototypes. As the sample density decreases, the average of the accuracy results
 54 gets lower, while the variance of the accuracy results gets larger. In other words, the class-specific
 55 prototypes in lower-density regions have a lower quality that may confuse the classifier.

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